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IN PROCESS INDUSTRY
EEM2023**

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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EEM2023

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FOOD SUPPLEMENTS – IS THERE A RISK OF VITAMIN AND MINERAL OVERDOSAGE?

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Abstract

Along with change of dietary habits, food supplements have emerged as one of possible intervention strategies to fight micronutrient deficiency. Despite the popularity of food supplements, the consumption of which has increased dramatically in the last few years, a plethora of associated risks inevitably follows. Vitamins and minerals, alone or in combination, present the most commonly used categories of food supplements and this paper reviews the occurrences of vitamins and minerals in doses higher than allowed, considering notifications registered on Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF) portal within 2011-2022 timeframe. Data related to selected classes of substances were manually extracted and evaluated in terms of compliance with regulation establishing maximum amounts of vitamins and minerals allowed in food supplements. Following this criterion, over a hundred notifications were recorded, revealing 113 cases of too high intake/risk of overdosage of vitamins and/or minerals. Non-compliances were not evenly distributed among these two groups of micronutrients, with 92% of violations referring to exceeded vitamins' tolerable upper intake levels, nor within the vitamins and minerals themselves. Too high intake of vitamin B6 was most often recorded (46 cases), followed by risk of overdosage/high intake of nicotinic acid (17), vitamin D (17), vitamin E (10), vitamin A (10), folic acid (2) and vitamin C (1). Notifications related to exceeded minerals' tolerable upper intake levels were significantly less represented and referred to the three minerals, zinc, iodine, and selenium, with a total of 9 recorded cases. In the notifications where the doses were stated, they sometimes exceed the recommended daily intake by hundreds or even thousands folds, and a case of poisoning (hypercalcemia) with one such supplement has also been recorded. The evaluation of the risk associated to the intake of high doses of vitamins and minerals from food supplements is particularly challenging due to frequent and different exposure sources. Therefore, improved quality control procedures and monitoring programs as well as adding complexity to the potential evaluation of the risk associated to the consumption of food supplements should be pursued in order to avoid undesirable products and resolve this problem in the best interest of public health.

Key words: food supplements, vitamins, minerals, overdosage.